

Towards a process of public tendering with automatic QTO for increased comparability of proposals: a prototype

GUIDO COUTINHO DE ALVARENGA

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Abstract

This study explores the application of OpenBIM to develop an automated quantity take-off (QTO) tool for structural elements in the context of public tendering processes. By leveraging open and neutral standards, particularly the Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), the tool aims to generate QTO tables that comply with the Portuguese Measurement Rules in Construction (Curso Sobre Regras de Medição na Construção, CSRMC). The primary focus is on reinforced concrete structures, including concrete volumes, rebar weights, and formwork areas.

The methodology begins with the development of a Python script, utilizing libraries such as IfcOpenShell, Pandas, and NumPy, to extract and manipulate quantities from IFC models. The script processes structural elements such as foundations, columns, beams, slabs, and reinforcing bars, calculating their base quantities based on project specifications. This process

is guided by the Level of Information Need and adheres to ISO 7817-1 standards to ensure model accuracy.

The study adopts the SECClass classification system and integrates it into a Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) aligned with CSRMC to facilitate data organization and interoperability. Furthermore, this study collaborated with the public procurement sector by integrating the QTO information requirements into a practical EIR, thereby ensuring the tool meets the specificities existing in this field.

This research demonstrates the potential of OpenBIM to streamline QTO processes, offering a transparent and efficient solution for public procurement in the construction industry.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/EFJMcEkWfPs>

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